

School Literacy Movement: A Literature Review

Dian Anisa Fitri¹, Sowiyah²

¹ Student Master of Educational Administration, Universitas Lampung, Indonesia

² Lecturer of Educational Administration, Universitas Lampung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine: (1) the context of the implementation of the school literacy movement program, (2) input on the implementation of the school literacy movement program, (3) the process of implementing the school literacy movement program, and (4) the product of the implementation of the school literacy movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung. The design of this study is an evaluation study using the Evaluation Model (CIPP) Context Input Process and Product. Data collection was carried out by interview, documentation, and observation techniques. The results showed that: (1) the context of the School Literacy Movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung was carried out in accordance with the regulation of the Minister of Education number 23 of 2015 concerning ethics which is classified as increasing student knowledge, student character, and student interest in reading, (2) input of the School Literacy Movement program in program scheduling, program funding and supporting facilities and infrastructure are classified as being in accordance with needs, (3) the School Literacy Movement program process has been carried out according to the plan but there are obstacles faced, namely in the form of not optimal socialization to students, lack of student motivation, and low student interest in reading, teachers have not received training related to literacy programs, teachers' views that School Literacy Movement interferes with class hours, and implementation time is still lacking. (4) the School Literacy Movement program product is in accordance with the objectives but there are still things that need to be improved, so the School Literacy Movement program at Baitul Jannah IT High School needs to be continued at the stage and in the following year with some improvements and some things that need to be improved.

KEYWORDS: CIPP Model Evaluation, Qualitative, School Literacy Movement Program.

INTRODUCTION

The results of PISA 2018 show a decrease in Indonesia's Literacy rating which was previously in 72 out of 78 countries to rank 74 out of 79 countries (PISA: 2018). Literacy is one of the important elements in the progress of the country in the era of globalization. The government has launched the National Literacy Movement, which is to improve the culture of literacy in education in families, schools, and communities with the aim of improving the quality of life through lifelong learning. The School Literacy Movement is one part of the National Literacy Movement carried out in schools where students, educators and education staff, as well as parents are involved in the activity. The results of the evaluation of the school literacy movement at SDN Rorotan 5 showed that the level of achievement of the School Literacy Movement reached 90.1% where students had carried out literacy activities very well as planned and expected by the teacher (Vanbela et al. : 2019). Evaluation of the school literacy movement at SD Muhammadiyah Wirobrajan 3 obtained results where the school literacy movement had an impact on the embedding of literacy culture to students (Maryani & Maryam: 2017).

According to the results of the evaluation of elementary-elementary schools in Tangerang Regency, it is revealed that literacy provides benefits where students become more enthusiastic about learning, the growth of love for the homeland, and the improvement of students' literacy skills (Magdalena et al. : 2019). The results of the evaluation of the School Literacy Movement in Public Elementary Schools throughout Panguat District show a GLS achievement level of 92.2%, which means that the School Literacy Movement has been running very well and is in accordance with government programs (Sitti Roskina et al. : 2019). According to the results of the evaluation of the school literacy movement at SD Kristen 04 Eben Haezer, it shows that the level of achievement of the School Literacy Movement is very good even though it still needs to be improved (Kurniadestrianto & Yari : 2020). The results of the evaluation that have been carried out provide a return to the school for the School Literacy Movement program that has been implemented and from that turn the school can develop and or make improvements in the School Literacy

Movement program in its schools so that it becomes better and provides more benefits for schools, students, teachers, educators and people in the school environment.

SMA IT Baitu Jannah Bandar Lampung has carried out various literacy activities such as literacy activities integrated in the lesson, pre-lesson literacy activities, library visits, awarding awards for students who stand out in the field of literacy, activities in the month of language and the provision of a reading corner in each class. Literacy activities at SMA IT Baitu Jannah Bandar Lampung have been carried out before the issuance of the minister of education regulation number 23 of 2015 which regulates the School Literacy Movement, but no evaluation of the School Literacy Movement has been carried out. From the evaluation benefits obtained from the evaluation activities, it is necessary to evaluate so that the school literacy movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung, which has never been evaluated, can provide the maximum possible benefits for schools, students, teachers, educators and people in the IT Baitu Jannah High School Bandar Lampung. Evaluation research is a scientific method carried out in order to obtain data aimed at knowing the effectiveness of projects, policies, and programs where later research results can be used as consideration to improve quality starting from the formulation, implementation, and results of projects, policies and programs. CIPP is a comprehensive framework for guiding the formative and summative evaluation of a project, programme, individual, product, institution, and system (Stufflebeam: 2003). So the evaluation of the School Literacy Movement that will be carried out at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung will be carried out using the CIPP model as a comprehensive evaluation model so that it can provide assessments and recommendations for the School Literacy Movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Ministry of Education and Culture carries out various literacy activities for the sake of achieving the improvement of the quality of life, competitiveness, development of the nation's character, and achieving the competencies needed in the 21st century. Literacy is deeply inherent in social life (Kalman : 2008). The literacy competencies needed in the 21st century include cultural and civic literacy, financial, digital, science, numeracy and language. Literacy skills can also be in the form of the ability to filter and process information so that it can be useful for humans (Nurhasanah, 2016). The National Literacy Movement has 3 domains, namely the Community Literacy Movement, the Family Literacy Movement, and the School Literacy Movement. The School Literacy Movement aims to foster student ethics through the cultivation of the school literacy ecosystem so that they become lifelong learning. Reading is an ability that must be possessed by children because through reading children can learn a lot about various fields of study. Therefore, reading is a skill that must be taught from the moment the child enters elementary school. The School Literacy Movement strengthens the movement for the growth of ethics as stated in the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 23 of 2015. One of the activities in the movement is "a 15-minute activity of reading non-lesson books before the study time begins". This activity is carried out to foster students' interest in reading and improve reading skills so that knowledge can be mastered better. The implementation of the School Literacy Movement through stages (1) habituation, (2) development, and (3) learning.

The School Literacy Movement is carried out by going through stages and adjusting readiness in each school. Readiness related to facilities and infrastructure, school residents, and other support systems. Evaluation has become an important part of various educational programs. Evaluation is important because evaluation is an activity carried out with the aim of providing an assessment in the preparation of plans, implementation processes and results of programs or policies (Asrori: 2014). The purpose of the evaluation is to obtain information about various aspects related to a program or policy (Asrori: 2014). The function of evaluation research is to find out how likely it is that it is that it is planned to implement, and how far the goals are achieved. Data from the results of this evaluation research is expected to be used to understand the effectiveness and efficiency of the School Literacy Movement Program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung. The CIPP evaluation model is an evaluation model developed by Stufflebeam in 1983 (Aziz et al.: 2018). The development of CIPP began in 1965 because public schools in the United States could not obtain a clear meaning in evaluating government-supported programs using gold standards for program evaluations (Stufflebeam: 2003). CIPP is a comprehensive framework to guide the formative and summative evaluation of projects, programmes, individuals, products, institutions, and systems. This CIPP model has been used throughout the United States and the world in short-term and long-term research. The CIPP model stands for context, input, processes, and products. The results of the

study that have similarities with this study are research entitled Evaluation of the Implementation of the School Literacy Movement at SD Muhammadiyah Wirobrajan 3 Yogyakarta City which was carried out using the CIPP model. This evaluation research shows the results that the School Literacy Movement has proven to be an effort to instill a culture of literacy. The literacy culture embedded in students makes students read more and process information well, and also students' writing and reading skills can also improve. Students also become skilled in connecting subject matter, in developing ideas and ideas, in understanding and solving problems, and the eventual hope that students can better master competencies in learning (Maryani & Maryam: 2017).

The similarity of this study is that they both evaluate the School Literacy Movement. The Evaluation Research of the School Literacy Movement Program at SDN Rorotan 05 North Jakarta City conducted with the CIPP evaluation model also has similarities with this research. The results of this study show that the School Literacy Movement program is based on permenkibud number 23 published in 2015. The School Literacy Movement is divided into 3 stages, namely habituation, development, and learning. Principals and teachers have implemented the program according to the indicators of the School Literacy Movement. The ability of the principal and teachers has been good in planning and implementing this program. Teachers who have been educated in undergraduates have received various trainings and workshops on the implementation of the School Literacy Movement program. The level of achievement of the School Literacy Movement program in schools is 90.01% which can be assessed in category A with the meaning that the implementation of the School Literacy Movement is very good according to plan (Vanbela et al. : 2019). Another research that has similarities with this research is an evaluation research entitled Evaluation of the Reading Culture Program in State Elementary Schools conducted at SD Negeri Tenganan. This evaluation research uses the CIPP model. The results showed that (1) reading culture is needed by students to practice skills in reading and writing, (2) the needs of schools to carry out literacy activities have been met with human resources, infrastructure that facilitates, funds, and work mechanisms that facilitate, (3) the process in implementing the program has run smoothly despite several obstacles, and (4) the program product has been achieved according to the initial plan even though there are activities that have not been achieved optimally (Sulistyo: 2017).

Another reference that has similarities with this research is a study entitled evaluation of the school literacy movement in public elementary schools in panguat sub-district. This research has a common evaluation model, namely CIPP, the difference in this research lies in the program being evaluated. The results of the evaluation of the literacy movement in state elementary schools throughout Panguat sub-district showed an achievement rate of 92.2%, which means that the School Literacy Movement has been running very well and is in accordance with government programs (Sitti Roskina et al. : 2019). Another similar research is a study with the title Evaluation of the School Literacy Movement Program at SD Kristen 04 Eben Haezer Salatiga with the results of the Literacy Movement has been running well which is supported by complete facilities and infrastructure, but there are still some obstacles related to its implementation (Kurniadesrianto & Yari: 2020). This research has similarities, namely evaluation research with the CIPP model.

Literacy which is an important element in the progress of the country has made the development of the National Literacy Movement Program. One part of the National Literacy Movement Program is the School Literacy Movement which involves all school residents. The School Literacy Movement program is an inseparable part of teaching and learning activities, therefore this program must always be developed to be able to provide benefits for all school residents. SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung has implemented the School Literacy Movement Program, but no evaluation research has been carried out to develop the program. To be able to develop this program, research was carried out on the Evaluation of the Literacy Movement Program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung, with the aim of providing information as a consideration in improving the quality of the program. The evaluation that will be carried out is the CIPP model where this model is considered to be able to provide complete information related to the School Literacy Movement Program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung. The results of this study are expected to provide an assessment and recommendation for the School Literacy Movement Program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is an evaluative research with a qualitative descriptive approach. The evaluation model used is the CIPP evaluation model. The CIPP evaluation model is considered to be an evaluation model that can evaluate a program comprehensively and can

provide useful information for decision-making considerations regarding a program, so that this evaluation research can provide recommendations regarding the planning and implementation of the School Literacy Movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung. Data collection in this study was carried out with interviews, observations, and documentation. Data analysis in this study uses data analysis techniques developed by Miles and Huberman. The steps taken in data analysis are (1) data reduction, (2) data display and, (3) conclusion and verification (Asrori: 2014). Validity is assessed through source triangulation and data collection technique triangulation. Source triangulation is done by asking the same thing to different sources. In this study, the sources of information from the data obtained were the principal, vice principal, librarian, teacher, and students of SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung. Triangulation techniques in data collection, which ask the same thing to the source in different ways.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of the context evaluation, namely the background of the implementation of the school literacy movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah bandar Lampung, is the emergence of Permendikbud Number 23 of 2013, the desire to increase students' interest in reading, ethics, and ability to literacy. The purpose of the school literacy movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah is to cultivate ethics, knowledge, and a love of reading in students. The input evaluation components include: (1) human resources, (2) supporting facilities and infrastructure, (3) funds or budgets, and (4) various procedures and rules required.

The results of the input evaluation, namely planning, are carried out through a meeting to discuss what activities will be carried out and what needs to be prepared in the implementation of the school literacy movement at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung. There has been no management of the school literacy movement has been compiled. In the implementation of each activity, the person in charge of each program has been appointed. The source of financing from the school literacy movement program comes from BOS funds, funds from foundations, and assistance from parents. The facilities and infrastructure in the school literacy movement program are obtained from BOS funds, grants from foundations, assistance from alumni, and donations from parents. The existing facilities and infrastructure to support the implementation of the school literacy movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung are sufficient. Even so, the school is still continuing to develop existing facilities and infrastructure. This is in line with the results of the research (Wandasari: 2017) input in the school literacy movement is an effort or activity that is participatory by involving all school residents.

The results of the evaluation process of the types of activities carried out in the school literacy movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah bandar Lampung are reading 15 minutes before students, library visit schedules, reading corners, literacy competitions, literacy in learning, language months, literacy in collaboration with publishers, visits to literacy centers, and making mading. Supporting factors for the program are (1) support and cooperation from school management, teachers and employees (2) available facilities and infrastructure, (3) support from parents, (4) support from the education office, (5) cooperation with book publishers, (6) and the existence of a thinking pattern of millennial teachers. Factors inhibiting the program are (1) lack of motives and interest of students in reading, (2) there is no training for teachers, (3) there is a view that school literacy movement activities interfere with learning, and (4) the time given is still lacking, (5) there is no librarian.

The results of the product evaluation of the objectives of the school literacy movement program at Baitul Jannah IT High School have been achieved, although there are several things that still need to be improved so that the results can be maximized. The result of the implementation of the program is the formation of student character, students' interest in reading increases, students' ability to understand questions increases, the emergence of various student achievements in literacy competitions, and the emergence of results such as clippings, collections of poems, and various children's works. The impact of the School Literacy Movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung is that students can think critically, students become happy to read books, and increase student achievement.

CONCLUSION

Based on research that has been carried out in evaluating the school literacy movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung using the CIPP model, it was concluded that: (1) The Context of the School Literacy Movement Program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung is needed to foster ethics, foster a sense of love of reading, and grow knowledge in students. (2) Input of the School Literacy Movement Program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung has been supported by planning,

financing, and facilities and infrastructure in accordance with standards. What still needs to be improved is the preparation of a School Literacy Team which will later ensure that the School Literacy Movement program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung can run well and in accordance with planning. (3) The school literacy movement process at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung has been carried out in accordance with the plan. The types of activities are reading activities 15 minutes before students, library visits, reading corners, literacy competitions, literacy activities in learning, language month activities, literacy activities in collaboration with publishers, and making mading. Supporting factors for the School Literacy Movement program are support and cooperation from school management, teachers, students, and librarians, available infrastructure, support from parents, support from the education office, cooperation with book publishers, and the thinking patterns of millennial teachers. The inhibiting factors of the School Literacy Movement program are the lack of motives and interest of students in reading, the absence of training for teachers, the view that the activities of the School Literacy Movement interfere with learning, the time given is still lacking for students. (4) The product of the School Literacy Movement Program at SMA IT Baitul Jannah Bandar Lampung is that the character of students is formed, students' interest in reading increases, students' ability to understand questions increases, the emergence of various student achievements in literacy competitions, and the emergence of results such as clippings, poetry collections, and various children's works.

REFERENCES

1. Aziz, S., Mahmood, M., & Rehman, Z. (2018). *Implementation of CIPP Model for Quality Evaluation at School Level: A Case Study*. Journal of Education and Educational Development, Vol. 5 No.1. p.1553.
2. Kalman, J. (2008). *Beyond defenition: central concepts for understanding literacy*. International Review of Education, Vol. 54 No. 5–6, 523–538.
3. Kurniadestrianto & Yari dwi kurnaningsih. (2020). *The Evaluation of The School Literacy Movement Program at Christian Elementary School 04 Eben Haezer*. Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, Vol. 11 No. 2 : 133-139.
4. Magdalena dkk. (2019). *Evaluasi GLS: Evaluasi Program Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah dasar wilayah kota dan kabupaten Tangerang*. Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar. Vol 4. No. 2: 230-248. Universitas Muhammadiyah Tangerang.
5. Maryani, I., & Maryam, S. (2017). *Evaluasi Pelaksanaan Gerakan Literasi Sekolah (GLS) di SD Muhammadiyah Wirobrajan 3 Kota Yogyakarta*. Seminar Nasional Bimbingan Konseling Universitas Ahmad Dahlan.
6. Nurhasanah, A. 2016. *Penggunaan Metode Simulasi dalam Pembelajaran Keterampilan Literasi Informasi IPS bagi Mahasiswa PGSD*. Jurnal Pendidikan Sekolah Dasar. Vol. 2 No. 1 87–95.
7. PISA. (2018). *PISA 2018 Results in Focus*. In OECD.
8. Sitti Roskina & Nofal K. (2019). *Evaluasi Gerakan Literasi di Sekolah Dasar*. Jurnal Manajemen dan supervisi pendidikan. Vol. 4 No. 1 : 541-4429. Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.
9. Sulisty, A. (2017). *Evaluasi Program Budaya Membaca Di Sekolah Dasar Negeri*. Kelola: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan, Vol 4 No. 1. p48-58.
10. Stufflebeam, D. L. (2003). *The CIPP Model for Evaluation*. *International Handbook of Educational Evaluation*. Vol 31–62.
11. Vanbela, V. T., Fuad, N., & Marini, A. (2019). *Evaluasi Program Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di SDN Rorotan 05 Kota Jakarta Utara*. Indonesian Journal of Primary Education, Vol 2 No. 2. p. 11963.
12. Wandasari, Y. 2017. *Implementasi Gerakan Literasi Sekolah (GLS) Sebagai Pembentuk Pendidikan Berkarakter*. JMKSP (Jurnal Manajemen, Kepemimpinan, dan Supervisi Pendidikan). Vol. 2 No. 2.